

Pricing as a Key Factor Used by Online Wholesaler and Retailers to Attract Online Consumers – A Study with Reference to Retail Industry in Bangalore Rural and Urban

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Abstract – The aim of this article is to emphasize the significance of pricing strategy in the online retail sector, and its effect on consumer behaviour. The aim is to test the relationship between online retailers' pricing strategies and customers' repurchase intentions in this context. Based on previous research, a questionnaire was designed and distributed to a sample of online respondents. This study adds to the literature by identifying and evaluating consumer loyalty and the repurchase intent influenced by pricing strategies' adopted by selected online retailers.

Keywords – Pricing strategy, online retailers, online customers, Customer loyalty, repurchase intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of the Internet is rapidly changing consumers' consumption preferences and promoting the significant growth of the E-commerce industry. One of the most common methods of shopping for convenience is online shopping. Indeed, among the Internet community, it is a common method of shopping (Bourlakis et al., 2008). Whether it is for clothing, appliances, or pets, the online shopping trend is growing in popularity. Every year, hundreds of websites and applications are developed and deployed to meet the growing demand for convenient shopping. If you're at home, in the workplace, or in another country, online shopping is becoming a viable option for all of your purchases. This is particularly true in developed countries, where every shop has a website from which you can purchase products. You can easily inform your customers of exclusive offers such as cash on delivery and exclusive discounts on online orders. This trend of shopping online from the comfort of your own home has recently caught on in Asia, especially in developing countries like India. India seems to have embraced the trend even more quickly than the rest of the world.

Customers from all over the world can sit at home and get what they want with a few mouse clicks and keyboard taps. They can choose their goods from a virtual multi-colored catalog. As a result, customers would not encounter issues such as "no stock" or "closing time" when purchasing goods across national and international borders. This viewpoint has introduced another aspect of EC, namely, hassle-free transactions. Shopping on the internet is easy, and the fact that it is available 24 hours a day, seven days a week adds to its appeal. It enables people to transcend time and distance to access global markets and business opportunities, thus opening up a new world of economic opportunity and growth.

Distinctiveness of online retailers

The principle of distinctiveness stems from the product level and applies to the same form of product with significant variations and no total substitution relationship (Waldman and Jensen, 2013). Product differentiation allows businesses to increase demand while decreasing price elasticity of demand in order to increase profits. According to the theory of monopoly rivalry, further product differentiation softens competition (Zhelobodko et al. 2012). Pricing power can be developed by businesses because the differentiation characteristics of commodities can form their market power for pricing a limited number of commodities. This distinction does not generally refer to physical differences between products, but rather to customers' perceptions of the distinction in sales venue, service quality, and other subjective perceptions. When customers purchase identical products from a few online retailers, the differentiated traits of different online retailers can shape differing degrees of attraction, reducing customers' price sensitivity (Graciola et al. 2018).

Pricing power

Consumers prefer to use the price of a commodity to determine the perceived quality of the product is one of the primary objective and how products are priced must be carefully considered. Profitability This can be accomplished by effective resource management and large corporations or a small business, product or service at a reasonable price. Pricing is the only aspect of the marketing in a high-quality sales profile; the other components produce costs and sales volume (Small Business Development Corporation, 2014).

Pricing - A success strategy for online retailers

The primary motivator affecting consumers who shop online is price. The principle of price tolerance has gained growing attention from researchers and managers in related pricing strategies. According to empirical studies, businesses should aim to maintain low price sensitivity in order to reduce customer behaviors that seek price

preferential treatments and thus increase profitability (Shankar and Krishnamurthi, 1996). Increased customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are two factors that contribute to increased price tolerance.

Pricing Strategies and Tactics

Pricing accurately is an important step in achieving and maximizing profit, as well as ensuring customer loyalty and repurchase. There are several pricing methods in use, each of which is based on a unique set of circumstances and parameters. There are some of the most widely used pricing methods. The following are the strategies used by online retailers in response to price changes:

- **Fixed-price strategy:** This technique has been used for a long time and assumes the implementation of constant rates for a long period of time.
- **Variable price strategy:** This strategy assumes a daily appeal to the sales promoting strategy through sales such that the price is adjusted in short periods of time.
- **The low price strategy:** It is used by stores that have no other advantages or strategic instruments aside from their rivals, do not sell post-sale facilities, and have a limited selection of emotions, with a focus on goods with a high turnover.
- **Rates at the same level:** This, in conjunction with the competition policy, means the practice of pricing at the same level as the rivals. Retailers who use this approach distinguish themselves from their rivals by emotions, in-store and post-sale facilities.
- **The high price strategy:** This is used by retailers when there is little competition or when they have significant advantages over their rivals, such as a strong location, a wide range of emotions, in-store and post-sale facilities, or a strong picture.
- **The unitary pricing strategy:** The manufacturer sets a price for each commodity and displays the price of a regular unit next to it. This technique is only applicable to items that can be measured with standard measurement units.
- **The brand level strategy:** This strategy entails setting prices at the level of each brand, with profit margins set based on the power of the brand and the contribution it will make to profit.
- **The commodity price-leveled strategy:** This strategy entails the retailer establishing a very low number of prices for items in the same category and categorizing those below those prices.

Pricing factor and Customer loyalty

Consumers play a critical role in a company's performance. The primary goal of organizations is to meet the defined needs of customers. Similarly, when deciding a suitable pricing plan, customers must be taken into account. Setting prices too low, though it will initially attract consumers, will not retain them in the long run because they will simply go elsewhere when cheaper prices are available. Online retailers must determine which customers they want to attract and develop retention strategies for these customers. Furthermore, when deciding which price to set, the

consumer's capacity and willingness to pay a certain amount for a product should be considered.

Loyalty is defined as a behavioral response expressed over time, and it is measured using metrics such as purchase proportion, purchase series, and purchase frequency. It is often seen as a function of variables such as customer comfort, satisfaction, and other perception factors. As a result, consumer loyalty can be thought of as a direct inducement of buying intention and action. Customers who are loyal to brand are more likely to praise it and recommend it to others. Customers who admire or favor retailers increase their purchases or are willing to pay a premium for them. Customers with high loyalty have low price flexibility and are willing to pay a premium to continue trading with their favorite retailers, whereas those with low loyalty concentrate only on the economic aspect. This implies that consumers with high levels of loyalty have less market flexibility, even with a significant source of extra profit for online retailers.

Pricing factor and Repurchase Intention

Repurchase purposes is a consumer's optimistic attitude toward an e-retailer that will result in repeat transactions (repeat buying behavior). According to Kim et al. (2012), repurchase intention means that consumers are interested in making a purchase using online shopping, that consumers' online shopping will be revisited in the future, and that consumers are interested in recommending online shopping because they already use it. Consumers trust the quality of goods sold in accordance with the price offered, the manufacturer provides discounts for branded products as opposed to competitor prices, the prices paid by retailers are fair, overall consumers are pleased with the price of the product, and consumers would accept information from experts on the price of the product to be purchased.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Njeru, J. M. (2017) stated that pricing strategy is critical for any entity involved in the manufacture of consumer goods and services because it provides information about the business and its products because a company does not set a single price but rather a pricing system that covers various items in its line. A pricing strategy considers segmentation, willingness to pay, market dynamics, competitor behaviour, trade margins, and input costs. A successful pricing strategy considers the consumer's, the company's, and the competitor's viewpoints, ensuring that an organization maintains a sustainable competitive advantage.

According to Fassnacht and Hussein (2013), a company should combine high prices with high promotion in order to increase profits while also attracting more customers. Furthermore, promotional deals on high-priced/high-quality products have a greater effect on sales of low-priced/high-quality brands than vice versa.

Yu and Wu (2007) mentioned that the internet allows people to purchase goods and services more easily. Online

shopping is very common in the Internet culture. One benefit of online shopping is that it provides customers with accurate details and a variety of options, allowing them to compare goods and prices online. The more options and convenience there are, the easier it is to find the desired product or service online. It has been discovered that online shopping offers greater gratification to modern-day shoppers who prefer convenience and speed.

Research Gap

Previous analysts have agreed that companies that adopt the right pricing strategies enjoy a long-term competitive advantage that reflects on their success. There have been very few studies on this subject that have centered on online retailing in the Indian context. The few studies conducted in India have concentrated on the food or clothing industries, leaving a research void in the retail industry. As a result, there is a need to conduct research in the Indian context, with a focus on e-retailing in Bangladesh. A thorough understanding of how pricing strategies are related to customer repurchase intent would contribute to the body of information in the online retail industry and among online consumers in general.

Statement of the Problem

According to Koller and Keller (2012), price is the only component of the marketing mix that generates revenue; the other components generate costs. They also noted that purchasing decisions are influenced by how customers view prices and what they believe the current actual price is. Understanding how consumers shape their price expectations is a critical marketing focus. Each pricing strategy has advantages and disadvantages, and there is no straightforward recommendation on which pricing strategy to use in combination with a specific product or market environment that benefits both consumers and retailers. This research looks at the impact of pricing factors used by online retailers to draw online customers.

Scope and Significance of the Study

Pricing techniques and consumer purchasing decisions are multifaceted phenomena; there is no industry-wide standard for conceptualizing and measuring them. As a result, each company must establish its own set of pricing strategies based on the reality of its competitive environment, past commitments, and anticipated requirements. Previous research has used a variety of methodologies to investigate the relationship between pricing policies and consumer purchasing decisions. As a result, another approach was required to resolve the problem in order to see the impact on consumer repurchase intention. This research will provide online retailers with competitive insight into how pricing strategies affect consumers' repurchase decisions. It will also inform them about how many of their rivals use similar pricing tactics, allowing them to position themselves competitively. Customers and the general public are also likely to benefit from the study by better understanding the different pricing techniques available while shopping online. This will be useful when they are

deciding what goods to buy, where to buy them, and how much they will spend.

Objectives Of The Study

- To study and comprehend the basics of online retailing and pricing factor used by online retailers
- To identify the pricing strategies and its impact on online customers

III. METHODOLOGY

The term "research methodology" refers to the systematic and scientific methods used to arrive at the results and conclusions of a study, which are then used to test claims of expertise. A methodology is therefore influenced by the viewpoints that the analysis chooses to study. This research is both descriptive and exploratory in nature, and it involves a variety of surveys and fact-finding inquiries. The primary goal of descriptive research is to explain the current state of affairs. This study describes the pricing of retail products relating to online business for online customers with special reference to retail industry in Bangalore.

Sample and Data Collection

The information used in this paper was gathered through a survey of online customers. Respondents were contacted online and asked to complete a questionnaire based on their most recent personal online shopping experiences. The first segment of the questionnaire assessed respondents' demographic details. The second portion of the questionnaire included elements to assess distinguishing characteristics such as cost-effectiveness, chargeless transactions, consumer satisfaction, and respondents' repurchase intention based on pricing strategies.

The primary data was collected using a five-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating Strongly Disagree, 2 indicating Disagree, 3 indicating Neither Disagree nor Agree, 4 indicating Agree, and 5 indicating Strongly Agree. A simple random sampling method was used for this research. Under this sampling design, the whole population has an equal chance of being included in the sample. To collect primary data, 125 (sample population) customers from selected online shopping sites (Ebay, Flipkart, Homeshop18, Snapdeal and Jabong) in Bangalore were interviewed. Data from the questionnaire was analyzed using SPSS 20 and various statistical methods such as Anova and Independent T-test were applied to determine the association of relationships between study variables.

Data Analysis

Independent T-Test

H₀: There is no significant difference in customer loyalty with different age groups

H_a: There is a significant difference in customer loyalty with different age groups

Table No – 1: Statistics Description

Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Below 30 Years	28	17.7500	2.91389	0.55067
Above 41 Years	16	15.5625	3.01040	0.75260

		Levene's test for equality of variances	t-test for equality means							
		f	sig	t	Df	Sig (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. error Difference	95% confidence interval of the difference	
									Lower	Upper
Quality of Service	Equal variances assumed	0.007	0.935	2.367	42	0.023	2.18750	0.92410	0.32258	4.05242
	Equal Variances not assumed			2.346	30.503	0.026	2.18750	0.93255	0.28430	4.09070

The above table shows that there is no significant difference between the significant values of the two groups. Also, the significant difference determined was 0.023 and 0.026 which was lesser than 0.05 (significant level). Hence, the significant value is lower than 5% level the null hypothesis is rejected and it has been proved that there is significant difference between the age of the respondents and customer loyalty. So, there is significant difference in customer loyalty with different age groups.

Analysis of Variance

H₀₂: Experience of the respondents has no significant difference among the saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction.

H_{a2}: Experience of the respondents has no significant difference among the saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction.

Table No – 2: Experience and Saving Money

	Sum of Squares	D.F.	Mean ²	F Value	P Value	S/NS
Between Groups	41.676	2	20.838	1.419	0.246	NS
Within Groups	1791.092	122	14.681			
Total	1832.768	124				

Source – SPSS Output

Table No – 3: Experience and Cost-Effective

	Sum of Squares	D.F.	Mean ²	F Value	P Value	S/NS
Between Groups	9.307	2	4.654	0.314	0.731	NS
Within Groups	1807.445	122	14.815			
Total	1816.752	124				

Source – SPSS Output

Table No – 4: Charge less Transaction

	Sum of Squares	D.F.	Mean ²	F Value	P Value	S/NS
Between Groups	4.539	2	2.269	0.181	0.834	NS
Within Groups	1527.989	122	15.525			
Total	1532.528	124				

Source – SPSS Output

One-way ANOVA used to find whether there is significant difference among the experience factor of the respondents and the study variable saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction. Since the p - value is greater than 5% level of significance for all the variables; we accept the null hypothesis for saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction and reject the alternate hypothesis. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference among experience factor and saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction.

Analysis of Variance

H₀₂: Monthly Income of the respondents has no significant difference among the customer loyalty and repurchase intention.

H_{a2}: Monthly Income of the respondents has no significant difference among the customer loyalty and repurchase intention.

Table No – 5: Monthly Income and Customer Loyalty

	Sum of Squares	D.F.	Mean ²	F Value	P Value	S/NS
Between Groups	75.141	2	37.750	4.359	0.015	S
Within Groups	1051.547	122	8.619			
Total	1126.688	124				

Source – SPSS Output

Table No – 6: Monthly Income and Re-purchase Intention

	Sum of Squares	D.F.	Mean ²	F Value	P Value	S/NS
Between Groups	5.451	2	2.726	0.341	0.712	NS
Within Groups	975.749	122	7.998			
Total	981.200	124				

Source – SPSS Output

One-way ANOVA used to find whether there is significant difference among the monthly income factor of the respondents and the study variable customer loyalty and repurchase intention. Since the p - value is lesser than 5% level of significance for customer loyalty, we reject the null hypothesis for customer loyalty and accept the alternate hypothesis. Hence, it is inferred that there is significant

difference among monthly income factor and customer loyalty. Since the p - value is larger than 5% level of significance for repurchase intention; we accept the null hypothesis for repurchase intention and reject the alternate hypothesis. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference among monthly income factor and repurchase intention.

IV. FINDINGS

- Independent T-Test shows that there is no significant difference between the significant values of the two groups. Also, the significant difference determined was 0.023 and 0.026 which was lesser than 0.05 (significant level). Hence, the significant value is lower than 5% level the null hypothesis is rejected and it has been proved that there is significant difference between the age of the respondents and customer loyalty. So, there is significant difference in customer loyalty with different age groups.
- One-way ANOVA used to find whether there is significant difference among the experience factor of the respondents and the study variable saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction. Since the p - value is greater than 5% level of significance for all the variables; we accept the null hypothesis for saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction and reject the alternate hypothesis. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference among experience factor and saving money, cost-effective and charge less transaction.
- One-way ANOVA used to find whether there is significant difference among the monthly income factor of the respondents and the study variable customer loyalty and repurchase intention. Since the p - value is lesser than 5% level of significance for customer loyalty, we reject the null hypothesis for customer loyalty and accept the alternate hypothesis. Hence, it is inferred that there is significant difference among monthly income factor and customer loyalty. Since the p - value is larger than 5% level of significance for repurchase intention; we accept the null hypothesis for repurchase intention and reject the alternate hypothesis. Hence, it is inferred that there is no significant difference among monthly income factor and repurchase intention.

Suggestions

- Online retailers must correctly consider the value of their product and develop various pricing strategies based on the value of their product in order to maximize profits.
- Managers of online retail stores must determine ways to influence customer decisions in order to thrive in the retail industry and appreciate consumer purchasing decisions.
- According to the findings, pricing strategies affect customer purchase intent. As a result, managers must develop tailored pricing strategies that enable the company to respond to evolving customer purchasing

decisions. Pricing strategies that are improved, especially those that include the consumer's viewpoint, create long-term competitive advantages for a company.

4. Giving a customer as much detail as possible allows for more informed decision making and the perception of adding a valuable service. Providing value to customers and increasing their level of awareness acts as a deterrent to losing customers. Managers should inform their customers about their pricing plans in order to influence their purchasing decisions.
5. Managers must devote as much organizational resources to implementing effective pricing strategies as they do to consumer acquisition and service initiatives. Pricing must be made a competitive capability in both online and offline stores.

V. LIMITATIONS

Since the data was collected online, there was no direct contact between the researcher and the respondents. Direct personal contact with the respondents would have enabled the researcher to extract additional details or clarification on some of the points raised in the questionnaire. The study is restricted to five e-commerce sites used by online shoppers in Bangalore. As a result, the study's results cannot be applied to the entire population of internet users in India. The sample size is limited as compared to Bangalore internet users. Estimates of different aspects of online shopping are derived from secondary sources, so the data's validity is often a constraint.

VI. CONCLUSION

The growth of online shopping has eroded online retailers' pricing strength. Adopting effective pricing strategy is a fundamental way for online retailers to maintain their growth and retain more customers, resulting in higher revenues. Online retailers can boost their market competitiveness by increasing differentiation, especially in commodity quality and logistics, which provides a new path for the formulation of marketing strategies for online retailers. Improving product and logistics quality has emerged as the primary direction for the future growth of online retailers, especially given that current online shopping demand from consumers emphasizes quality, pricing, and service. Improving the quality of products and setting reasonable prices are critical for attracting repeat customers and building customer loyalty. Finally, enhancing the security of online transactions, as well as paying attention to protecting consumers' personal information and transaction information privacy, will effectively draw customers' loyalty and increase their willingness to pay.

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